

A PROPOSED HIRF TEST FACILITY FOR AIRCRAFT TESTING

Diane R. Kempf
Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division
Patuxent River, Maryland

ABSTRACT

Since the high power threat from friendly and foreign emitters continues to grow and the threat of High Power Microwave (HPM) is becoming more of a concern, the Department of Defense (DOD) has been interested in developing a capability to efficiently and thoroughly test aircraft for this High Intensity Radiated Field (HIRF) electromagnetic environment. There are technical challenges and safety concerns to test the electromagnetic immunity of aircraft. A hybrid Transverse Electromagnetic (TEM)/Reverberation chamber has been proposed by NIST and pursued by the Army and the Navy. This paper discusses the general concept of a TEM/reverberation chamber, the work that has been done to develop one, and the plans by the Army and the Navy to build a TEM/reverberation facility.

INTRODUCTION

For many years, the DOD has had full spectrum (10 kHz to 40 GHz) electromagnetic (EM) immunity requirements for aircraft. The Navy must routinely operate fixed and rotary wing aircraft in a dense, high intensity electromagnetic environment (EME). The Army also must operate rotary wing aircraft and other systems in a severe EME. The high power threat from friendly and foreign emitters continues to grow and the threat of High Power Microwave (HPM) is becoming more of a concern. Recently, the

Federal Aviation Administration and the European Joint Aviation Authorities have jointly revised the HIRF certification requirement for commercial aircraft. Testing to these higher power requirements is both a technical challenge and a safety concern.

While several test techniques are currently available to evaluate the EM immunity of aircraft and aircraft systems, all have one or more significant limitations. As a result, the DOD has been interested in developing a cost effective, robust, full spectrum, ambient isolated test capability.

In 1988/89, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) proposed a hybrid TEM cell/ reverberation chamber test facility to meet Army EM test requirements. A facility was planned to be built by the Army at the Electronic Proving Ground at Ft. Huachuca, Arizona. The design for the full scale facility was 65% completed, however, the program was terminated in 1993.

The basis for the concept is that, individually, TEM cells at low frequencies, and reverberation chambers at high frequencies, have demonstrated cost effective performance. NIST noted several technical and facility issues as well as a scalability risk for a hybrid test facility. [1] Navy funded investigations have addressed the technical and facility issues as well as the scalability.

A modification of the NIST facility concept is planned to be built as a joint Army/Navy project at the Naval Air Warfare Center (NAWC), Patuxent River, MD, the lead laboratory for DOD aircraft EM testing. Also, a separate, but associated man-in-the-loop simulation facility will permit monitored, power on, full threat level testing.

This paper discusses the general concept of the Army/Navy hybrid TEM/reverberation facility and proposed development plans.

FACILITY CONCEPT

The present techniques for testing aircraft typically utilize anechoic chambers or outdoor test facilities. Both techniques are costly and limited in capability. Anechoic material is extremely expensive. As the electromagnetic field strength requirements increase, the cost of the field generating sources also increases. In a TEM/reverberation chamber, there is no power lost through absorption by anechoic material or by radiation into the surrounding area as at an outdoor site, so much smaller power sources can provide the same field intensity on the aircraft under test. Also, anechoic material is limited in the amount of power that it can absorb before it becomes combustible, and the fumes of combustion are extremely deadly. The hazards to test personnel, other equipment and the overall environment increase as the field strength requirements increase. Anechoic and outdoor test facilities provide very limited illumination of the aircraft for each antenna position. Therefore, in order to thoroughly test an aircraft, many antenna positions must be used, as seen in Figure 1. This is very time consuming and still only provides limited illumination and aspect angles of field entry into the aircraft. A reverberation chamber immerses the aircraft uniformly in the field so that all aspect angles and polarizations are tested at the same time as seen in Figure 2.

Anechoic Chamber

Outdoor Test Facility

Figure 1.

Reverberation Chamber

Figure 2.

A TEM cell large enough to test an aircraft would provide testing in the frequency range of 10 kHz to 20 MHz. A reverberation chamber of the same size can be used in the 20 MHz to 40 GHz frequency range. The concept of combining the two test facilities into one chamber would provide testing of aircraft in the entire 10 kHz to 40 GHz frequency range. (See figure 3.)

Figure 3.

In the TEM frequency region, the aircraft is in a linearly polarized, far field, plane wave environment. In the reverberation operating region, the aircraft is immersed in an isotropic and randomly polarized field. In the TEM operating region, both horizontal and vertical polarizations can be achieved, but the aircraft would have to be moved or rotated in order to provide multiple aspect angles of the field. Still, the time savings in testing would be significant, since more of the aircraft would be illuminated at one time than in an anechoic chamber or an outside test facility. More time savings also could be achieved through the use of the Band Limited White Gaussian Noise (BLWGN) technique, also known as "frequency stirring". [2] This is electronic mode-stirring rather than the conventional mechanical mode-stirring, both of which are performed in a reflective chamber. In the BLWGN technique, the item under test is

radiated with white gaussian noise limited to a bandwidth of typically 1 MHz to 50 MHz so that sweep speeds can be 100 times faster or more. [3]

PLANS

The NIST facility concept which was planned to be built by the Army is now planned to be built as a joint Army/Navy project at the Naval Air Warfare Center Aircraft Division (NAWCAD), Patuxent River, MD, the lead laboratory for DOD aircraft electromagnetic (EM) testing. All of the Army aircraft Electromagnetic Environmental Effects (E³) testing is presently being done at NAWCAD Pax River. Pax now has the complete Air Combat Environment Test and Evaluation Facility (ACETEF). This includes: an outdoor test site, an anechoic chamber, a shielded hanger, a man-in-the-loop capability, motion/manned flight simulators, and the computer capability to tie it all together. Adding a TEM/reverberation facility to this, all combat systems could be evaluated for all threats and environments in a very efficient and cost effective manner.

The original planned Army facility is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4.

After NIST proposed the concept of a hybrid facility, a 1/10 scale prototype was built and evaluated in 1990. [1] NIST noted several technical and facility issues and a scalability risk for a hybrid test facility. Navy funded investigations have addressed these issues. Since 1990, there has been a lot of theoretical work performed on the statistics and theory of the TEM operating region, the reverberation operating region, and the transition region between them. A Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) sponsored by the Navy at the NSWC, Dahlgren and performed by Science and Engineering Associates (SEA) developed the theory in detail. Based on the findings, modifications to the design will provide better field uniformity and less test uncertainty, especially in the transition region. Another Navy SBIR, also performed by SEA, studied these findings in order to determine how the original NIST design could incorporate the theoretical findings to improve the test capability of the proposed facility. Phase II for these SBIR's will further investigate these findings and verify the theory by testing. A prototype for testing is also planned. If the prototype is large enough, it will provide an interim aircraft test facility.

The proposed Army/Navy facility will include the test chamber, adjacent lab spaces, RF sources, test fixtures and instrumentation. Also, a separate, but associated man-in-the-loop simulation facility will permit power on, full threat level testing while the aircraft cockpit and subsystems are monitored to determine the effects of the HIRF environments.

The project presently has been officially recognized as a future MILCON which allows the project to receive DOD funding. In addition to funding through the SBIR program, funding is being pursued under the Combined Test and Evaluation Investment Program (CTEIP) and the Test Technology Development and Demonstration Program (TTD&D).

SUMMARY

A hybrid TEM/reverberation facility would fulfill the need for a capability to efficiently and thoroughly test DOD and commercial aircraft for the HIRF electromagnetic environment. Adding a TEM/reverberation facility to the present capabilities at Pax, would make it possible for all aircraft and combat systems to be evaluated for all threats and environments in a very efficient and cost effective manner.

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